

ANALYSING THE INTERNATIONAL MARKET FOR PROJECT "CARDIO VESSEL" AND USING IT IN PRACTICE

NURJABOVA DILAFRUZ SHUKRULLAEVNA

TASHKENT UNIVERSITY OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES
KARSHI BRANCH, INDEPENDENT RESEARCHER OF DEPARTMENT
"SOFTWARE ENGINEERING"
KARSHI, UZBEKISTAN

dilyaranur1986@gmail.com

+998939060772

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7127470>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 25th September 2022

Accepted: 27th September 2022

Online: 30th September 2022

KEY WORDS

*design of Software, architecture
Software, CJM, and Customer
development.*

ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on task automation for the Cardio Vessel project, based on which a platform-independent model of object-oriented software architecture is developed for the Cardio Vessel project within a model-oriented approach.

According to the World Health Organization

(https://www.who.int/cardioescence_diseases/ru/), 17.5 million people die every year from cardiovascular diseases. More than 75% of these deaths occur in low- and middle-income countries. According to these statistics, early heart attacks and cardiovascular disease can be prevented by 80%. The treatment of cardiovascular diseases and the correct diagnosis are very expensive. The chronographic "golden diagnostic method" is widely used in Uzbekistan at the Research Institute of Cardiology. This work has been studied by scholars such as Alfa Cuarteroni, Manzoni A., Vergara S., F. N. Vande Vosse Eindhoven Italy, and the Netherlands. However, since problems in the network of atherosclerotic vessels in the treatment of cardiovascular diseases still exist, doctors need software. In Uzbekistan, the "golden diagnostic method" of coronography is widely used in the Research Institute of Cardiology.

Following the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of February 26, 2003 "On measures to further reform the healthcare system" PR-3214 of February 26, 2003, and the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 140 of March 17, 2003, the Research Institute of Cardiology and the 15th City Clinical hospital, established based on the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5216 dated October 30, 2017 - National Database of Legal Documents, October 30, 2017, No. 17.06.5216/0187) with additions and changes. Republican Center for the Development of Medical Education of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan project "Improvement of the healthcare system (Health-3)" COLLECTION OF CLINICAL PROTOCOLS ON CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES for doctors of district and city medical associations following the order of the Minister of Health No. 57 dated February 1, 2016, PR. The main goal of the RICM organization is

to provide qualified cardiological care to the population at the level of international standards and to introduce modern methods of treating and diagnosing cardiological patients into healthcare practice.

At the Institute of Scientific Expertise of Cardiology of Uzbekistan, the main tests required by the patient can be performed directly in the laboratory, which reduces the length of the patient's stay in the hospital. Such examinations include 24 - hour ECG monitoring, a test with physical activity on a bicycle ergometer and a treadmill, determination of echo ECG, cholesterol and its fractions, sugar profile, determination of glycated hemoglobin, a study of platelet aggregation activity, and study of endothelial functions. In direct cooperation with the trauma center. Vokhidov Institute allows to carry out

complex examinations necessary for the patient (coronary angiography, myocardial scintigraphy to assess the reserve of coronary circulation) and treatment methods (coronary angioplasty and stenting). But the software to solve the above problem helps to solve 85 % of the problem in cardiology.

Why is this topic relevant, in the world many people suffer from diseases of the cardiovascular system? Our father and mother, great-grandparents, a newborn child fell ill with some kind of heart symptom or a person fell ill and many suffer. What to do will have to go to the doctor with your own feet without registration, wait for your live queue, open a story on paper, and so on, real problems who like it. We get nervous and new problems appear and we get worse and worse.

Fig.1. Object and subject for “Cardio vessel”

Doctors complain that they don't have automated systems and how tired everything is. Let me know if any of you have experienced this problem. I do not want my program to remain in some computer and stand as a tick. I have gone through all of these. In time, I talked a lot

with patients, about what was wrong, what should I add, that I don't like the way the doctors treat me, and how much it takes to go to the road to come and go back. On the Internet, when I checked on requests with keywords: atherosclerosis treatment.

Fig2. Analysing the international market for project “cardio vessel”

Treatment of atherosclerosis mobile version	Countries	Index	%
1.	Russia	16848	102%
2.	Ukraine	99	88%
3.	Kazakhstan	134	53%
4	Kyrgyzstan	13	42%

Table 1. About all cardio illnesses for project Cardio Vessel

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